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INTRODUCTION

Motivation

Traditional bonding processes require high-temperature ovens, leading to:

- high energy consumption
- long curing cycles
- scalability challenges for large components

Aim

To develop a scalable, energy-efficient bonding process for composite materials using CNT-enhanced epoxy adhesives.

METHODOLOGY

- Sample preparation and electrical characterisation
- Local curing and IR thermal imaging
- Single lap tensile test (ISO 4587)

- Thermal transient FEA via Representative Volume Element (RVE)

RESULTS

Resistance before and after CNT alignment

Temperature profile along the length of the aligned and randomly dispersed CNT 400 specimens

Infrared imaging of temperature distribution during Joule heating-based curing

Comparison of shear strength of single-lap specimens and pure epoxy adhesives

SEM results after lap-shear tests

Randomly dispersed CNT

Aligned CNT

FEA temperature distribution of RVE models

Maximum and average temperatures from transient thermal FEA of RVE models

Most of the results presented in this poster have recently been published in the *Polymers* journal. Further findings and insights can be found in the article: Dragasiute, K.; Monastyreckis, G.; Zeleniakiene, D. *Electrically Conductive Nanoparticle-Enhanced Epoxy Adhesives for Localised Joule Heating-Based Curing in Composite Bonding*. *Polymers* 2025, 17, 1176. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym17091176>.

CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that CNT-enhanced epoxy adhesives enable effective Joule heating-based curing in composites. Optimal CNT loading (0.5 wt%) improved conductivity, shear strength, and heat localisation. Alignment methods further enhanced targeted heating efficiency. Overall, CNTs enable efficient, localised curing with improved mechanical bonding properties.

FUTURE RESEARCH

The next stage of this research will investigate electrically conductive MXene nanoparticles for localised Joule heating in structural composites. Ti_3C_2Tx coatings and interlayers will be used, supported by advanced nanocomposite technologies to produce materials with enhanced properties and reduced energy demand, contributing to more sustainable solutions.

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